

Volatile Enforcement of Road Traffic Regulations in Vientiane

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Abstract: Traffic accident has increased in Lao PDR, especially in Vientiane in the last decade due to lack of compliance to traffic regulations. Vientiane is the capital of Lao PDR which presents the highest number of accidents annually comparing to other provinces because of weak enforcement of the regulations, weak infrastructure that hampers authority to comply the regulations severely, and boom of motorcycles that notably became the first factor of accident. This research is set to examine the compliance of road traffic regulations, because, despite the measurement taken by the government but the accident is increasing. Therefore, to what extent weak compliance of road traffic regulation in Vientiane? The study used the data base existed in Vientiane through analysis of Laws, cases and previous empirical studies. The weakness of the compliance is interconnected with several reasons, such as lack provisions of the Law, negligence of regulations and weak infrastructure.

Keywords: Weak enforcement, road traffic regulations, accident and Vientiane.

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Introduction

Traffic regulation has a tremendous role for administrating circulation and road safety in a country. But the increase of vehicles and weak infrastructure is challenging the management of road traffic safety, especially the Least Developed countries which present badly a number of accidents. Lao PDR is among the countries which has borne mostly road traffic accident because of its unreliable compliance of regulation,¹ therefore many vehicles user violate the laws remarkably the motorcycles utilizer.² Many provinces of Lao PDR are touched by this road traffic trauma,

¹ Accordingly, between 2008 to 2021, the number of accidents in Lao PDR is increasing per year with number of 700 to 14945, available at <https://data.aseanstats.org/indicator/ASE.TRP.ROD.E.031>

² <https://www.countryreports.org/country/Laos/traffic.htm>

especially during the celebration of new year on which many accidents occurred because drunk driving and high-speed driving, and also there a lot of illegal driving.³

In Lao PDR, the traffic regulation is determined by the road traffic law adopted by the National Assembly on 8 April 2000 and law on public road adopted on 3 April 1999. These regulations formulating administration of road traffic safety over the country, they stipulate frame of traffic regulation by providing the rules of driving, road code, prohibition of illegal driving, road authority controllers and determination of differences of road in terms of using them. Meanwhile, road traffic is the movement of people or the use of various types of vehicles in lines of surface communication and transportation within the country,⁴ and traffic regulation is a detailed regulation that tells road users how to strictly comply with regulations.⁵ In number The road traffic in Lao PDR is under the Law. All road users in Vientiane are required to abide by such laws and adopt the concept of traffic system especially the mechanism of signals that tell how to follow the road traffic including symbols⁶. Accordingly, all travelers or road users in Vientiane, Lao citizens, aliens, stateless person and foreign persons who travel on the roads within the territory of the Lao PDR must strictly respect and adhere to the road traffic law and other traffic regulations,⁷ In the view of the law on public road, the traffic regulation exist in various public road such as national public roads; public roads in provinces, prefecture and special zones, district public roads, municipal public roads, rural roads and specific roads.⁸

Therefore, the study focuses relatively all roads mentioned above existing in Vientiane. Over the surface of Vientiane there many types of roads which are under the road traffic regulation enforced; however, the non-compliance of the rules by the intent of the road users and negligence of the authority worsens the safeguard of road safety.⁹

Research Methodology

This research applies a doctrinal methodology through analysis of legal rules existing in Vientiane as well as a best worldwide best practice to inspire improvement of the trend of traffic regulations in Vientiane. It globally referred on the view of the laws on road traffic law and public road law, penal code and other important rules. The weak enforcement of the regulation is not actually because of the provisions of existing law but the compliance over the stakeholders including road authorities. Therefore, this study applied as well the case study approach in order to point out the evolvement and factors of volatile traffic regulation in Vientiane. In addition, the study based on previous empirical research is also important to refer on perception of other authors idea and recommendation in facing the circumstances of the country because weak traffic regulation has been long time, preciously since the booming of population that increase of vehicles and vehicles users over the capital at the same time.

Literature review

³ A report affirmed that 238 were victims of road traffic accident during the celebration of new year in 2019 that is a bit decreasing comparing to previous year, meanwhile the traffic regulation is relatively bad.

⁴ See art 2 paragraph 1 of the road traffic law of the Lao PDR adopted on 8 April 2000

⁵ See Ibid paragraph 2

⁶ It is range of symbols installed, engraved, written or drawn on the surface of the road, on the shoulder, at the roadside, or above a road to warn and to facilitate traffic.

⁷ See art 4 of the road traffic law of the Lao PDR adopted on 8 April, and see also article 4 of the law on public road stipulates al road users have the obligation to comply with traffic order.

⁸ See article 5 of the law on public road adopted by National Assembly on 3 April 1999

⁹ Dr.Jai Shankar Singh and Kartikeya Kumar Singh, (2018) "The motor vehicle act 1988: A critical evaluation" International Journal of innovative research and advanced studies, Vol.5, 2

Non-compliance of traffic regulation is not a new trend either developing countries or the Least of developed countries, but it has existed. The study conducted by Dr. Jai Shankar Singh and Kartikeya Kumar Singh (2018) on a critical evaluation of the motor vehicle shows that negligence of road traffic engenders accidents that kill more people than other disease annually, especially motor vehicles accident which is growing day by day. Oelrich Nell (1974), evoked that the number of fatalities caused by negligence of traffic regulation is as worse as fatality damage occasioned by epidemic and war; it demonstrated on his research, despite good infrastructure particularly road in south Africa but the road accident is increasing and omnipresent.¹⁰ Harwinder Kaur (2022) stated in his work road traffic accident and related factors that weak compliance of traffic regulation encourages vehicle users to use aged vehicles and lack of safety precaution, carelessness and driving while intoxicated. He also stressed One of the reasons is a lack of sensitivity and responsibility on the part of state authorities. The human sensibility and life-respecting emotions of state officials, to investigate situations on the roads such as malfunctioning traffic lights, also causes accidents if not properly maintained.¹¹ Kristle Young et al. (2007) conducted a review of aspects of in-vehicle driver distraction, focusing specifically on mobile phone use, and concluded that this device has received the most attention in the driver distraction literature. According to Omar and Ashawesh (2008), road traffic accidents will rise to third place in the list of major causes of death and disability by 2020 world over. In responding that non-compliance of regulation leads a disorder and fatalities in road safety, WHO (2017), during its workshop on safe systems and police enforcement for road safety in select pacific island countries, expressed the revision of legislation to reduce the blood alcohol concentration and strength role of enforcement and road policing as part of the update of the public road safety, operationalize essential equipment to develop national capacity for enforcing legislation against drink-driving and speeding.¹² And it encourages furtherly member states to introduce safe systems principles and approaches for road safety to high-level national stakeholders for consideration of adoption and implementation as part of national strategies and programmes, strengthen police data systems to cover injuries, deaths, enforcement operations and risk factors. Police investigation and data reporting of non-injury/damage-only crashes should be discouraged as a hindrance to limited police resources, strengthen coordinated intersectoral collaboration between relevant national road safety stakeholders, including clearly defining the scope of police roles in road safety and adopt model legislation for major behavioural risk factors including speed, alcohol, helmets, seat belts, child restraints.

Lao PDR is not exception, in the view of research conducted by Tania Vogel, Daniel Reinharz and Marissa Gripenberg about an organizational analysis of road traffic crash prevention to explain the difficulty of national program in Low income country that the implementation of road safety in Lao is the weak relationship between stakeholders, particularly in the area of collective action and is reinforced by lack of interest from the stakeholders.¹³ As result of this the authors proposed as solution the strengthen collaboration between stakeholders in ameliorating effectiveness of traffic regulations. Anousack Thammavong and Boualinh Soysouvah, (2016) the problem of traffic system is in Vientiane is the bad traffic control and management system.¹⁴ Thanousorn Vongpraseuth, Eun Yeong Song

¹⁰ Oelrich Nell, B.A., M.Ed. (1974), "accident liability and primary process thinking: a study in ego psychology"

¹¹ Harwinder Kaur (2022), Road traffic accident and related factors review,

¹² WHO (2018) workshop on safe systems and police enforcement for road safety in select pacific island countries

¹³ Tania Vogel, Daniel Reinharz, Marissa Gripenberg and Hubert Barennes, (2015) "an organizational analysis of road traffic crash prevention to explain the difficulty of national program in low-income country", BMC research notes

¹⁴ Anousack Thammavong and Boualinh Soysouvah, (2016) "optimization of traffic signal time and coordination for road network with oversaturated", vol 5, 1.,

and Chang Gyu Choi added that management of traffic is become serious problem in Laos due to increase of vehicle users and unreliable traffic regulation.¹⁵

Objective

Traffic regulation is very crucial in developing countries. It is one of the key points of sustainable development goals because it involves in people`s lives. A lot of developing and LDC suffer from damage caused by traffic accident.¹⁶ Volatile compliance of the traffic regulation in Lao is causing ubiquity traffic trauma almost in its provinces, especially Vientiane province that leads this research to show up the weak enforcement of road traffic regulation by stressing the role of stakeholders particularly the road authorities, as well as the public road users from negligence of the rules. Meanwhile, the aim of the research is to indicate problems relating to weak compliance of the regulation either the laws itself does not figure the important scenario leading weak management of traffic accident or the authorities and road users do not engage to comply the regulations.

Discussion and recommendation

1. Traffic administration system in Vientiane

Traffic administration in Vientiane has been implemented since the enforcement of the regulation relating to public road law and road traffic law both mentioned above as well as the penal code which prohibits and punishes road traffic violation¹⁷. Statistically road traffic trauma causing death is more dangerous than other pandemic since it exists daily and almost every country according to constatation of WHO in its annually report on road accident.¹⁸ Therefore, talking about volatility of traffic regulation compliance in Vientiane, this part evokes the management of traffic regulation over public roads around

1.1. Management of traffic regulation over public roads

The law on Public Road defines the regulations and measures to the management, use, ensure security and smooth traffic.¹⁹ This law determines explicitly the public road in the country, especially in Vientiane which is subject of discussion in this research. Accordingly, there are classifications of public roads as follows: national public roads; public roads in provinces; prefectures and special zones; districts public roads; municipal roads; rural roads; specific roads.²⁰ Following this classification, the study focused more on the management of district public roads existing in Vientiane provinces relating to traffic regulations system,²¹ and municipal roads which is the most subject of this study because it is mostly used by a number of people in Vientiane.²² Meanwhile the administration of these roads enumerated above are under the control of the authority and available for public use, means all people citizens or

¹⁵ Thanousom Vongpraseuth, Euth Yeong Song and Chang Gyu Choi, (2022), mode of transport and inequity in Least developed country: the case of Vientiane Lao PDR", 2022, 14, 5959. <https://doi.org/10.390/su14105959>

¹⁶ Vadim Avdeevich Avdeev and Oleg Pavlovich Gribunov (2020), "legal basis for ensuring transport security", journal of critical review, vol.7, 13.,

¹⁷ For e.g., art 84 of the penal code of Lao PDR "Any person intentionally damaging or obstructing roads, modifying or damaging traffic signs, signals, or kilometer marks, or using violence or threats against vehicle drivers, thereby causing a traffic accident, shall be punished by six months to two years of imprisonment and shall be fined from 100000 Kip to 1000000 kip.

¹⁸ See WHO annually report on traffic accident fatalities

¹⁹ See art.1 of the Public Road

²⁰ See art.5 of the ibid

²¹ District public road is a road important for economic political, and socio-cultural development, and for national defense and security at the district level, including: roads between districts, roads connecting municipalities within a district to villages, ports, tourism places, historic sites and special zones within the district.

²² This class of road refers to system of road used for traffic within a municipal area.

foreigners who have fulfilled public road using requirement are free and equal to use these said roads with accord to the regulations.²³

All people live permanent or non-permanent who use vehicles has to comply strictly with traffic regulations under the road traffic law of Lao PDR, and this latter additionally bans all action intend to cause obstruction or may engender an accident.²⁴ The application of these laws is under the control of ministry of communications, transportations, posts and constructions officials which is represented by the public road police and traffic police.²⁵ The police traffic execute facilitation and control of traffic in Vientiane with respect of their requirements as state authority.²⁶ In the basis, they control mechanized vehicles or vehicles not run by engines; accordingly, it is required for mechanized vehicles to comply with technical standards of the manufacturer factory and regulations provided by concerned ministry. Article 7 of the said Law determines the requirements for mechanized vehicles, as same as the vehicles not run by engines which is stipulated by article 8 of the law.

A part from these above, the law provides clearly the state of vehicles can be used in order to avoid any trauma in public road or other obstruction of traffic safety, and also the licenses because not all unauthorized person could not use vehicle cross the public road. The law determines the age bicycles drivers must be no younger than twelve years old, the motorcycle must not be lesser than fifteen years old for motorcycle 110 cc but for more than must be eighteen years old,²⁷ and it is no permitted more than two persons to ride with regard of wearing helmets. A driver of passenger transport must be at least twenty-five years old with driving license obtained after passing fully the required test and has to respect the over transporting passengers or goods.²⁸ If the vehicle has broken down on the road, the driver must be responsible for removing that vehicle from lanes of traffic.

In the case of violation of these traffic regulations, the public road police or traffic police is necessary to detain offender, seize or detain vehicles has violated the road traffic regulation in Vientiane, and undertake the case processing at the police.²⁹ In case of the accident occurring it is compulsory to undertake inspection, make a record, and collect document for investigation as well as interrogation.

1.2. Punishment of traffic regulation offence

According to traffic regulations in Vientiane the offender is punished following the serosity of his offence; the punishment surrounds on fines if any persons commits these violations as follows: violating traffic light, violating traffic signals; fail to have a driver's license or not have vehicle documents, driving in the wrong direction, driving while intoxicated, fail turn on light during the night time, driving a vehicle without break, create obstruction of roads, fail to wear helmets and transport in excess weight limits.³⁰ There is also a criminal punishment while the vehicle user committing traffic safety offense, violating the road traffic law that causing accident, injury, disability and death.

The penal code of the Lao PDR determines criminal responsibility of offender according to classification of offence that he had committed. There is responsibility for commission of traffic security which compounds an offence result in severe injuries or physical disability, the offender shall be punished by two to five years of imprisonment and

²³ See the view of art.4: All Lao Citizens, aliens, stateless persons, and foreign persons who travel on the roads within the territory of the Lao PDR must strictly respect and adhere the road traffic law and traffic regulation.

²⁴ See article 5 of the Law on road traffic law of the Lao PDR

²⁵ See art. 6 of the Ibid

²⁶ During the function of their missions, public road police and road traffic police have to wear uniform and badges, and notably be Courtois.

²⁷ See art.10 of Ibid

²⁸ See art 11 of Ibid

²⁹ See art 25, para.2, of ibid

³⁰ See art.36 of ibid

shall be fined from 200,000 Kip to 2,000,000 Kip;³¹ an offence results in the loss of life, the offender shall be punished by six to ten years of imprisonment and shall be fined from 300,000 Kip to 3,000,000 Kip;³² an offence is committed negligently, the offender shall be punished by a fine of 50,000 Kip to 300,000 Kip; an offence is committed negligently and results in severe injuries, injuries to several persons or physical disability, the offender shall be punished by six months to three years of imprisonment and shall be fined from 100,000 Kip to 1,000,000 Kip; an offence is committed negligently and results in the loss of life, the offender shall be punished by two to five years of imprisonment and shall be fined from 200,000 Kip to 2,000,000 Kip and an offence is committed negligently and results in the loss of many lives, the offender shall be punished by five to eight years of imprisonment and shall be fined from 500,000 Kip to 5,000,000 Kip. In the other hand there is also a commission for traffic regulation resulting in accidents which are: violation causing accidents and injury to other persons shall be fined from 50,000 Kip to 300,000 Kip; an offence results in severe injuries, injuries to several persons or physical disability, the offender shall be punished by six months to three years of imprisonment and shall be fined from 100,000 Kip to 500,000 Kip; an offence results in the loss of life, the offender shall be punished by two to five years of imprisonment and shall be fined from 150,000 Kip to 700,000 Kip; an offence results in the loss of many lives, the offender shall be punished by five to ten years of imprisonment and shall be fined from 200,000 Kip to 1,000,000 Kip.³³

2. Main factors of the volatility of traffic

Considering these enumerated traffic regulations in Lao PDR, in fact these laws provide suffice regulations to safeguard road safety in Vientiane, but its compliance with reality and enforcement is become debatable context over the capital. As known, the number of populations in the country is increasing that blatantly makes the vehicle users augmenting.³⁴ As a result of this, the traffic regulations is become fragile because of uncontrollable vehicle users and negligent of police.

2.1. Negligence of traffic regulation

In the modern society, act of negligence has become a main cause of trauma, particularly in traffic accident.³⁵ Although the criminal or penal code of the given country punishes it but its ubiquity occurs almost daily in the society. The research found, motorcyclists' users in Vientiane are very negligent in reading and obeying traffic signs and using mobile phone while riding that led often accident. It is argued that there is an urgent need to rectify the situation by interventions at all possible levels. According to hospital-based injury surveillance in Vientiane, the majority of patient in the hospital are child; according to survey conducted by Sysavanh Phomma-chanh et al. before some college, they talk on mobile while riding on the public road.³⁶ The young motorcycle tends to neglect the regulation while riding, some survey also confirmed the calling while riding motorcycle especially school students.³⁷ Not only motorcycles but young drivers generate risky of traffic accident while driving, some research evoked the many young drivers engage in

³¹ See art. 85, para.2 of the penal code of Lao PDR

³² See *ibid* par.3

³³ See art 85 of the *ibid*

³⁴ NOLINTHA, Vanthana, (2011). "Cities, SEZs and connectivity in Major Provinces of Laos." In *intra- and inter-city connectivity in the Mekong Region*, edited by Masani Ishida, BRC Research Report No.6, Bangkok Research Center, IDE-JETRO, Bangkok, Thailand.

³⁵ Dr. Jai Shankar Singh, (2018) "The motor vehicle act 1998: A critical evaluation" *International journal of innovative research and advanced studies*, vol.5,2,.

³⁶ Taylor & Francis, (2017) "sustainable development goals road traffic injuries: The new research challenge", *International journal of injury control and safety promotion*, vol.24, No.2, 143-144, available at <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/epdf/10.1080/17457300.2017.1313924?needAccess=true&role=button>

³⁷ Long T. Truong, Hnag T.T. Nguyen and Chris De Gryute, (2018) "correlations between mobile phone use and other risky behaviours while riding a motorcycle", *Vol. 118, P. 125-130*, available at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2018.06.015>

such risky driving behaviors which risk of crash. Further survey affirmed that only 64% of motorcycle drivers wear helmets more likely female but the most threatening situation is 10% of child passengers wear helmets, and the use of helmets its days is decreasing especially during the evening and running with red traffic light in the evening.³⁸ In fact almost $\frac{3}{4}$ of drivers in Vientiane daily break speed limits and almost third of motorcyclists have been drinking alcohol.

The driving while drunk also is among a negligence of the traffic regulation since the road traffic and penal prohibit this offence still many people in Vientiane repeating this. The result of some survey affirmed that the many high school students are engaging in consumption of alcohol means that most of people in the capital are putting their selves in risky behaviors,³⁹ because they often uncontrol high speed while driving. In addition, driving while drunk leads also aggressive driving which frequently causes accident occasioning jeopardize of human life and property. Beerlao affirmed that Laos has high rate of road accident compared to other countries in the region with motorcycle involved in 95% of all vehicular accident and making up 90 % of fatalities. In fac 90% of the accident involves in drunk driving, speeding and other violations of traffic laws,⁴⁰ especially during the weekends or while there is occasion together drinking alcohol.

Alex kremer, world Bank manager in Lao PDR said “road safety is major health issue, just like the eradication of dengue or malaria”. “The hard data on driver behavior and accident unfortunately confirm tragic personal experiences of thousands of Lao people, and obviously it will take leadership, commitment, time, and sustained effort to make our roads safe.” To eradicate violation of traffic regulation in Vientiane still big challenges for the government in regarding the perspective of concerned authorities in the capital. Expressly, over thousand of people are died on the roads in Laos annually, with many more suffering physical injuries and trauma after crashes. So far, the number and severity of crashes has been increasing which statistically about to rise by 35% between 2010 and 2020, while it has continued up to now despite any measures applied by the authorities.

In fact, negligence of traffic regulation is due to weak enforcement of the law. It’s the role authority such as the minister concerned and road police or traffic police to enforce the regulation to hamper vehicle users from violating the rules negligently.⁴¹ The strict enforcement of regulation can be proceeded and can assure definitely safety of road traffic, but the road police themselves release road users to violate the rules. In the case of drivers forget vehicle document or high speeding, they police do not take measure while the offender offers some money. This kind of practice makes difficult challenges to eradicate the road accident in the capital. In addition, as affirmed above, most of vehicle drivers have been to drink alcohol every evening that makes the police tired of controlling the drunk-driving.

2.2. Weak Infrastructure

According to perspective of some authors and reality of road infrastructure, Laos is among countries has very bad road infrastructure that easily occasion accident to vehicle driver and it also amplify traffic obstruction. In fact, Traffic in Laos is chaotic, and road conditions are very rough. Few roads have lane markings. Where lane markings, road signs, and stoplights do exist, they are widely ignored. Theoretically, traffic moves on the right, but vehicles use all parts of the road. Motorcyclists pay little or no heed to cars. Motorcycles carry as many as five people, greatly impeding the drivers' ability to react to traffic. The evening hours are particularly dangerous. Road construction sites

³⁸ The world bank (2021), speeding, driving under the influence of alcohol common among drivers in Vientiane, road safety survey finds, available at <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2021/11/18/speeding-driving-under-the-influence-of-alcohol-common-among-drivers-in-vientiane-road-safety-survey-finds>

³⁹ Master dissertation “alcohol drinking among high school students of sikhottabong district Vientiane capital, Lao PDR, available at http://ethesisarchive.library.tu.ac.th/thesis/2017/TU_2017_6017090124_8928_8381.pdf

⁴⁰ <https://www.beerlao.la/newsroom/police-step-up-road-safety-campaign/>

⁴¹ Krige Siebrits, Sphia Du Plessis and Ada Jansen, (2020) “The limits of laws: traffic law enforcement in south Africa”, South African journal of economic and management sciences, Vol.23, No.1, available at <https://journals.co.za/doi/10.4102/sajems.v23i1.3430>

are poorly marked, appear with no advance warning, and can be difficult to see at night.⁴² As a result, the cause of accident is not only because of the users but the government also does not take its engagement to repair broken road and widen it in order to ensure safety of people while using the public road.

3. Ameliorating traffic regulation in Vientiane

3.1. Implementing austere regulation

Sysavanh Phonmm-chanh recommended the stricter regulation in enforcement of the traffic regulation. Therefore, the laws are relatively enough to administrate road traffic regulation in Vientiane what lack is the enforcement austere of the Laos so that all vehicle drivers respect the rules. Strictness of the enforcement should base on the education of people not violate the regulations, treat all vehicle drivers equal without discrimination whoever commits the rules. As stated above the most occurring case drunk driving, riding without helmet, and high speeding driving; so, the police should be required to control and punish severely drunk driving, meanwhile the government should help the road police to detect and facilitate control of alcohol drinking before driving. Based on the culture of people, concerned authorities should sensibilized the area not to obey the law. The concerned authority also should apply for measures to encouraging people from not wearing helmet and not use mobile phone while driving because these are the main factors of traffic violation.

3.2. Improving function of road authority

In face of the situation in Vientiane the authority should enforce the law and implement prevention of accident causing by negligence of traffic regulations. The public road police should refer their control on normality of driving by which the driver should be obliged to avoid unsafe activities and reactions⁴³. Driving behavior is the leading cause of traffic fatalities⁴⁴. Therefore, preventing aggressive or dangerous driving attitudes is a critical first step toward taking action for decreasing them. For improving the safety of roads, it is important to evaluate an individual's driving style and identify aggressive conduct. Recommendations must be made for guiding drivers toward normal driving behavior⁴⁵. In addition, aggressive driving is considered the driver's behavior categorization or pattern that includes normal speeding and inconsistent or excessive acceleration and deceleration, which is a significant cause in more than 90% of road crashes

In fact, the pretext of normal driving style is determined as driving with no dangerous behaviors and without the qualities listed in aggressive driving, careless driving, alcoholic driving, and drowsy driving⁴⁶. However, some study states a secure driving style as one in which the driver correctly focuses on driving⁴⁷. Rapid changes in acceleration or speed, tailgating, dangerous lane changes, improper vehicle lateral position, driving when drunk or tired, and inattention to the driving activity must all be avoided in a normal driving style.

⁴² Traffic and road conditions in Laos, <https://www.countryreports.org/country/Laos/traffic.htm>

⁴³ Senderal, M.; Chethiyar, S.D.M.; Azmi, M.B. (2021) Factors of Aggressive Behavior among Motorcycle Drivers and Its Relationship with Dangerous Driving Index in the State of Penang. *J. Correct.*, 4, 1–10.

⁴⁴ Waseela, M.; Laosee, O. (2015) Determinants of road traffic injury among adult motorcyclists in Malé, Maldives. *Asia Pac. J. Public Health*, 27, 277–285.

⁴⁵ Sadeghi-Bazargani, H.; Abedi, L.; Mahini, M.; Amiri, S.; Khorasani-Zavareh, D. (2015), Adult attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder, risky behaviors, and motorcycle injuries: A case-control study. *Neuropsychiatr. Dis. Treat.* 11, 2049–2054.

⁴⁶ Hussin, Z.; Ahmad, S.R. (2021) Exploring Two Types of Aggressive Behavioural Risk Factors among Illegal Motorcycle Street Racers in Malaysia. *Int. J. Criminol. Sociol.* 10, 784–794

⁴⁷ Carmona Fernández, J.; García Fernández, F.; Martín Gómez, D.; de la Escalera, A.; Armingol Moreno, J.M. (2015), Data fusion for driver behaviour analysis. *15*, 25968–25991

The road police should be stricter in these following driving style such as aggressive driving which firstly consist of driving likely to endanger life by raising the probability of a collision. Hostility, annoyance, impatience, or a desire to save time are common motivators for this conduct. Abrupt and anomalous changes in the speed of the vehicle, tailgating, dangerous lane changes, improper vehicle lateral position, and quick deceleration and acceleration take-off or braking are all examples of dangerous driving styles⁴⁸. Aggressive driving style is also associated with driving excessively fast, recklessly overtaking or driving aggressively, infrequent use of brakes, vehicle wobbling on the road, delayed acceleration or gear change, and exceeding speed limits. In addition, it is important to accentuate improvement of control on visual-feature-based driving behavior identification approaches are very sensitive to light conditions. Despite the use of contemporary cameras, significant changes in light intensity reduce the precision of such procedures. Intrusive technologies or cameras may upset the driver. Image processing necessitates a large amount of computer power, making it unsuitable for real-time applications and embedded systems in automobiles. Driving behavior recognition systems depending on non-visual features, on the other hand, require little processing resources, yet have low accuracy. As a result, we propose a strategy depending on the driver's non-visual characteristics, which provides great efficiency and accuracy. And secondly, the road police should control very scrupulously a dangerous driving which is a deliberate deviation from safe driving⁴⁹. It includes a wide range of on-road violations such as speeding and dangerous overtaking, among others. As all these behaviors are linked with accident involvement and can cause injuries to the driver, passengers, and other people on the road, as well as economic, property, and road infrastructure damages, they deserve attention from a traffic safety perspective.

Conclusion

The increase of accident in Vientiane is actually a result of weak enforcement of traffic regulations. This trend is occasioning the commission of road traffic violations above, as well as other violations not cited in this research. By this end the concerned authority should take strict measure to eradicate this detrimental trend by developing national capacity for enforcing or implementing safest systems approaches to road safety; for example the organization of workshop on enhanced enforcement and effective road policing because throughout the workshop the stakeholders could point out the major subjects relating to amelioration of road traffic safety based on behavioral risk factors, standard operating procedures for roadside enforcement, operational data and intelligence-driven enforcement, crash scene investigation, enforcement equipment, and engagement of external stakeholders. In addition, the workshop may gather also the concerned authorities even the private stakeholders to sharing technical knowledge on safe systems for road safety including the scientific evidence base that underpins effective road safety policy; to sharing technical knowledge on effective road policing and enforcement strategies; and to developing enhanced enforcement strategies and procedures applicable to the situation in participating countries, particularly for speed and alcohol infringements.

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⁴⁸ Goh, W.C.; Leong, L.V.; Cheah, R.J.X. (2020) Assessing Significant Factors Affecting Risky Riding Behaviors of Motorcyclists. *10*, 6608

⁴⁹ Ronquillo-Cana, C.J.; Pancardo, P.; Silva, M.; Hernández-Nolasco, J.A.; Garcia-Constantino, M. (2022) Fuzzy system to assess dangerous driving: A multidisciplinary approach. *22*, 3655.

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